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POST-SPINNING CLICK CROSSLINKED BIOBASED POLYURETHANE COAXIAL NANOFIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Two biobased thermoplastic polyurethanes with maleimide and thiol moieties (PU-MAL and PU-SH) were electrospun in coaxial configuration and subsequently crosslinked across the interface via thiol-maleimide Michael addition to obtain homogeneous and non-soluble nanofibers. PU-MAL and PU-SH were firstly synthesized using both solvent and catalyst-free procedure and co-electrospun in stoichiometric ratio as core and sheath, respectively. Post-spinning click reaction of the nanofibers led to tough membranes, exhibiting almost 50% increase in Young modulus and three times higher both tensile strength and elongation at break values. Clicked nanofibers of ~350 nm in diameter presented regular surface morphology, resistance to organic solvents and enhanced hydrophobic character. Finally, a membrane containing an excess of thiol groups was electrospun to be, on one hand, functionalized with 1H,1H,2H-Perfluoro-1-decene to improve its

hydrophobicity and on the other used as synthesized for the adsorption of AgNPs from aqueous solution. These results demonstrated that our proposal led to strong membranes with tailored characteristics, suitable for applications with solvent resistance, hydrophobicity and adsorption requirements, such as wastewater treatment.

Introduction

Polymeric electrospun nanofibers are polyvalent materials ready to be functionalized thanks to their high surface to volume ratio ¹⁻³. Among them, biobased polymeric nanofibers had attracted increasing attention during the last decade due to sustainability concerns ^{4,5}. Numerous biobased polymers have been processed as electrospun fibrous membranes showing, nevertheless, low spinnability and poor mechanical properties, mainly due to their chain rigidity, gelation and high conductivity ⁶⁻⁹. This is why, a miscible synthetic polymer is usually used as support to obtain, at the end, partially biobased membranes with the desired properties ^{10,11}. However, miscibility problems often arise, resulting in jet instability issues and subsequent low quality nanofibers. In this context, crosslinking of those electrospun nanofibers appears necessary in order to achieve competitive performance.

As well-known and easily intuitive, electrospinning and crosslinking of polymers are not so compatible words. Since crosslinked polymers are, by definition, insoluble and, hence, not processable by electrospinning, time and energy consuming processes, such as sintering, or multi-step process involving the use of initiators become necessary ¹²⁻¹⁷. One possibility to overcome this limitation is the so called on-the-fly or post-electrospinning crosslinking of the nanofibers ^{18,19}.

Co-electrospinning has recently emerged as an innovative configuration for the production of technologically advanced nanofibers through a simple one-step process. Indeed, numerous variations of co-electrospinning have been developed to produce multifunctional nanofibers with

applicability in numerous fields, and, in particular in biomedicine, due to the easy encapsulation of functional molecules, bioactive compounds or drugs ²⁰⁻²⁶. Among them, coaxial electrospinning, that is, electrospinning of separate polymeric solutions in a coaxial disposition to a final unique nanofiber, allows for a more versatile configuration of the nanofibers in which just one composition is exposed towards the external environment, while the inner one is usually used as substrate in the so-called mix and match properties ²⁷. This configuration lead to multifunctional nanofibers and it is also used for the production of crosslinked nanofibrous membranes ^{28,29}.

During the last years click chemistry has established as a powerful tool aligned with greener approaching of materials design, with fast and quantitative reaction yields under mild conditions and without undesired by-products. Indeed, it has been widely applied for the crosslinking of polymers either using crosslinkers or by properly functionalized complementary polymers thus avoiding the use of a third compound ³⁰⁻³³. Among the click reactions, the thiol-maleimide Michael addition stands out, since it runs at room temperature, without any metallic catalyst and the variety of chemical compound that can be used as crosslinkers is considerable ³⁴⁻³⁷. However, literature dealing with the production of crosslinkable nanofibers using click chemistry is scarce ¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Two relevant studies were carried out, producing water insoluble nanofibers by their on-the-fly crosslinking through catalyst-free azide-alkyne Huisgen cycloaddition, for tissue engineering applications ^{38,39}. Besides, Kalaoglu-Altan et al. used the thiol-ene reaction for the on-the-fly crosslinking between poly(2-alkyl-2-oxazoline) and tetrakis(3-mercaptopropionate) electrospun nanofibers ⁴⁰.

In this work, two biobased polyurethane were synthesized with pendant maleimide (Michael acceptor) and thiol (Michael donor) and co-electrospun in core/sheath configuration, to obtain nanofibrous membrane that was subsequently click crosslinked. The main objective was the

assessment of the developed synthesis and post-electrospinning click crosslinking strategy for the fabrication and strengthening of novel biobased nanofibers. Indeed, just few works have been reported in the literature that address the fabrication of post-spinning cross-linked nanofibers. The work of Ozlem I. Kalaoglu-Altan et al.⁴⁰ targeted the spatially controlled functionalization of the membranes through click chemistry using dyes, while the work of I. González de Torre et al.³⁸ and the work of A. Fernández-Colino et al.³⁹ focus on tissue engineering application. The present work aims to produce a crosslinked membrane with excellent mechanical properties and solvent resistance, which can be further functionalized (through click chemistry) for applications requiring these features. To do so, the morphology, dynamic mechanical behaviour, mechanical properties, surface hydrophobicity and solvent resistant of both crosslinked and not-crosslinked membranes were determined. Finally, a nanofibrous membrane with an excess of thiol was produced and its ability to adsorb silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) was characterized. Furthermore, the same electrospun composition was functionalized using a hydrophobic fluorinated alkene (1H,1H,2H-Perfluoro-1-decene) to improve its hydrophobicity.

Methods

Synthesis of N-(2,3-dihydroxypropyl) maleimide (DHPM)

In a 250 mL bottom flask, 10 g (0.06 mol) of Exo-3,6-epoxy-1,2,3,6-tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (Furan-A) were dissolved in 30 mL of EtOH. The solution was vigorously stirred throughout the process. In a separate vial, 5.65 g (0.062 mol) of (±)-3-amino-1,2-propanediol (APO) were dissolved in 15 mL of EtOH and subsequently added dropwise to the Furan-A solution. The mixture was refluxed at 85 °C for 24 h. Initially, the solution was transparent and turned turbid orange at the end. After the reaction, the mixture was cooled down at room

temperature and a white solid precipitated was formed. The white solid, N-(2,3-dihydroxy-propyl)-10-oxa-4-aza-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]-dec-8-ene-3,5-dione (DHPM-A, 232 g mol⁻¹) was collected by vacuum filtration, washed with EtOH and dried under vacuum at 45 °C for 24 h. The yield was assessed at 60.2%. Then, DHPM-A was deprotected through the retro-Diels-Alder reaction. To that end, in a 250 mL bottom round flask 2.5 g of DHPM-A were dissolved in 50 mL of toluene and refluxed at 125 °C for 7 h. The solution was then let cooling at room temperature overnight in order to recrystallize. A white solid, N-(2,3-dihydroxypropyl) maleimide, (DHPM, 174 g mol⁻¹) was collected through vacuum filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum at 60 °C for 24 h. The reaction yield was 73%. ¹H NMR and FTIR spectra of DHPM are shown in Figure S1.

Synthesis of PU-MAL and PU-SH

The polyurethanes were synthesized using a two-step or prepolymer bulk polymerization method, following a previously reported protocol ⁴¹. Briefly, semicrystalline poly(butylene sebacate)diol (PBSD) was melted in a two-necked round flask purged with N₂, 1,6-Hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) was added, mechanically stirred at 90 rpm, and left it to react at 90 °C for 2 h. Then, the chain extender (DHPM for PU-MAL and 3-mercapto-1,2-propanediol for PU-SH) was added to the prepolymer, mixed vigorously at 150 rpm for 10 min, and after that, the viscous liquid was transferred to a mould and pressed at 50 bar and 100 °C for 13 h to complete the polymerization. Squared films of 90 x 90 mm² and 1.4 mm thick were produced. The polyol:diisocyanate:chain extender ratio was set on 1:6:5 in both cases and no catalyst was used. The synthesized PU-SH and PU-MAL have a renewable carbon content of 50 and 47%, respectively.

Coaxial and single electrospinning of PU-MAL and PU-SH

PU-MAL and PU-SH films were cut in small pieces and dissolved separately in DMF:CHCl₃ (2:1 v/v) at different polymer concentrations, 15 wt% for PU-SH (0.148 mEq of thiol per g of solution) and 20 wt% for PU-MAL (0.186 mEq of maleimide per g of solution). Additionally, 0.05 mL of Triethylamine (TEA) was added to 5 mL of the PU-SH solution, to promote the click reaction, since small amount of weak base facilitates the nucleophilic thiolate anion formation and, thus, initiates the reaction cycle. The electrospinning parameters were set on: 18 cm tip to collector distance, 10 kV voltage and 1.4 ml h⁻¹ and 1.1 ml h⁻¹ flow rates for PU-SH (sheath) and PU-MAL (core), respectively. The coaxial electrospinning process lasted approximately 1 h, resulting in nanofibrous membranes with mean thickness of $242 \pm 36 \mu\text{m}$. Then, the nanofibers membrane was irradiated with UV-light at 365 nm for 90 minutes in order to complete the click reaction. The resulting membranes (called from now on MALcoSH and clicked-MALcoSH) were let dry 1 day and then analysed. All the analysis were performed on the same samples of membrane before and after the click reaction. When PU-SH and PU-MAL were electrospun separately, the same electrospinning solutions and parameters were used, just adjusting the flow rate to 1.2 ml h⁻¹. Another membrane with excess of thiols was produced, using the same electrospinning parameters except for the flow rate, that was set to 1.5 ml h⁻¹ for PU-SH (sheath) and 1 ml h⁻¹ for PU-MAL (core) producing a membrane with an excess of thiol groups. The electrospun membrane underwent the same irradiation process presented before to obtain the so called thiolated clicked-MALcoSH.

Organic solvent resistance

The chemical resistance of the membranes towards different organic solvents was tested exposing the crosslinked membranes to six different solvents: ethanol (EtOH), toluene, metil-2-pirrolidone (NMP), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), dichloromethane (DCM) and tetrahydrofuran

(THF). The samples were weighted, inserted in a closed vial containing the solvent, sealed and left 1 week. Then they were dried at 40 °C under vacuum during 24 h and weighted again. The gel fraction content was calculated using the following equation:

$$Gel\ content\ (\%) = \frac{m_1}{m_0} \times 100$$

Where m_1 is the mass after extraction and m_0 is the initial mass of the sample.

The chemical resistance of the membranes was also visually tested submerging them in the same solvent mixture used for the electrospinning. In a typical experiment, 10 mg of each membrane was put in a 3 mL solution of DMF:CHCl₃ 2:1 v/v in a closed vial and removed after two hours to be analysed.

Adsorption of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs)

The ability of the membrane to adsorb AgNPs was corroborated submerging 10 mg of the membrane containing an excess of thiol groups in 1 mL of AgNPs dispersion (0,02 mg mL⁻¹). The adsorption was monitored using UV-vis spectroscopy, following the decreasing signal of the characteristic peak of AgNPs at 408 nm.

Functionalization with 1H,1H,2H-Perfluoro-1-decene

The membrane was functionalized submerging it in a solution containing an excess of 1H,1H,2H-Perfluoro-1-decene (P1D). To prepare the solution 1 mL of P1D was dispersed in 10 mL of methanol and sonicated during 20 minutes. Then it was used as batch solution and diluted depending on the amount of membrane to be functionalized, maintaining always a molar ratio

between the thiol theoretically available on the nanofibrous membrane and the PID of 1:10. The membrane were let 2 h on the PID solution and then wash with a large excess of methanol and EtOH and dried in vacuum at room temperature, before use.

Results and Discussion

PU-MAL and PU-SH polyurethanes were synthesized following the prepolymer bulk polymerization method. The hard segment weight percent, determined by the ratio of diisocyanate and chain extender over the total weight of the polyurethane components, was 35 wt% for PU-MAL and 30 wt% for PU-SH. Thus, the theoretical content of maleimide and thiol groups in PU-MAL and PU-SH were around 9 wt% and 3 wt%, respectively. The polyurethanes were characterized by FTIR (Figure 1A). As it could be observed, the majority of the peaks were identical for the two polymers, given by the use of the same polyol and diisocyanate. However, the two characteristic peaks of maleimide at 829 and 697 cm^{-1} related to the =C-H out-of-plane and in-plane bending, respectively, were only present in the PU-MAL spectrum^{42,43}. The absence of the characteristic peak associated to the isocyanate at 2270 cm^{-1} confirmed the successful synthesis of both PUs. It is worthy to note that the stretching vibration of thiol group, around 2550 cm^{-1} in FTIR, it is known to be hardly identifiable due to its weak intensity⁴⁴, even more with a weight percentage as low as that used in this composition. The similarity of the compositions can be also deduced from the ^1H NMR spectra (Figure 1B). The characteristic peaks of the polyol were found at 1.3 ppm, 1.6 ppm, 1.7 ppm and 4.1 ppm, while those of the diisocyanate were at 1.5 ppm and 3.2 ppm. Since the chain extender differed just for the pendant group, the signal of the two methylene groups at 3.3 ppm and the one of methine at 3.6 ppm were observed in both spectra.

Finally, the characteristic peaks of the different pendant clickable groups were identified respectively at 6.7 ppm for the maleimide cycle of PU-MAL and a small peak at 1.8 for the thiol group of PU-SH.

The molecular weight of the produced polyurethanes was also measured. For PU-SH Mw, Mn and PDI of 148 kDa, 43kDa and 3.3 were obtained, respectively. For PU-MAL, an Mw of 26 kDa, Mn of 10 kDa, and a PDI of 2.6 were calculated. Both polymers were then analysed by DSC (Figure 1C). As can be seen, PU-SH and PU-MAL showed one endothermic peak, at 74.5 °C (ΔH_m of 62.5 J g⁻¹) and 78.7 °C (ΔH_m of 65.5 J g⁻¹), respectively, which was assigned to the melting of their soft segment^{41,45}. None of the polyurethanes showed any melting peak associated to the hard segment. This could be appointed to the steric hindrance of the maleimide and thiol groups in both chain extenders that could had prevented the formation of inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonds between the urethane groups. This fact might also explain the good solubility of both polymers. Moreover, the thermal stability of the material was analysed by TGA (Figure S3). The characterization results allowed us to conclude the success of the designed synthesis route of the functional counterpart polyurethanes.

Figure 1. Characterization of PU-SH and PU-MAL polyurethanes: A) FTIR, B) ¹H NMR and C) DSC analysis.

PU-MAL and PU-SH polymeric solutions were first separately electrospun in order to study their spinnability. The obtained nanofibers were analysed by SEM (Figure 2). The PU-SH showed good spinnability, resulting in homogeneous nanofibers with narrow diameter distribution (212 ± 17 nm) and without beads. On the contrary, the electrospinning of PU-MAL was harder and worse overall quality nanofibers were obtained, with larger mean diameter and wider diameter

distribution (548 ± 67 nm) as well as with presence of some beads. Several different electrospinning condition were tested to obtain better PU-MAL nanofibers but with not satisfactory results, probably due to the low molecular weight of this composition.

Figure 2. SEM images of the electrospun PU-SH (spinning condition: 15 cm tip-to-collector distance, 9 kV electric field and 1 ml h⁻¹ flow rate) and PU-MAL (spinning condition: 15 cm tip-to-collector distance, 12 kV electric field and 1 ml h⁻¹ flow rate) nanofibers.

In a core/sheath nanofiber configuration, the polymer composition with the best electrospinnability is usually chosen as sheath layer, so that the viscous traction facilitates the spinning of the core layer. For the same reason, the flow rate of the sheath solution is usually higher than that of the core⁴⁶. Therefore, attending to the better spinnability of PU-SH assessed by SEM, it was selected as the sheath layer for the subsequent coaxial electrospinning of both solutions, while the PU-MAL was the core one. The flow rates and the solution weight percentages were set in order to assure the best quality of the nanofibers and, at the same time, an equal molar ratio of maleimide and thiol groups.

The coaxial MALcoSH nanofibers' membranes were successfully obtained and, as explained, their UV light mediated post-electrospinning thiol-maleimide crosslinking (Figure S5) was conducted. The occurrence of the thiol-Michael click reaction between the thiol and maleimide

groups and the consequent crosslinking of the co-electrospun nanofibers was assessed by several techniques. Taking into account that the chemical structure of the two polyurethanes was identical except for the chain extender (Figure S4) and, at the same time, the maleimide moiety could be monitored easily by ^1H NMR and FTIR, the disappearance of the peaks related to the maleimide and thiol was taken as evidence of the click reaction. In order to perform the ^1H NMR of the crosslinked nanofibers, a thin layer of clicked-MALcoSH was submerged in d-CHCl_3 , left under vigorous stirring at 40°C for 24 h and analysed. In Figure 3A, it could be seen that the ^1H NMR spectrum of the MALcoSH presented the characteristic maleimide related peak at 6.7 ppm and the one of thiol at 1.8 ppm. After the click reaction, those peaks completely disappeared, while the other peaks remained mainly unaffected, thus confirming the successful thiol-Michael reaction between the polymers inside the nanofibers without undesirable side reactions. Besides, the FTIR spectra (Figure 3B) showed similar evidences. Indeed, the characteristic peaks of maleimide at 829 and 697 cm^{-1} were clearly visible in case of MALcoSH spectrum, while they were not detected in that of the clicked-MALcoSH. As expected, no other appreciable change was found on the remaining peaks of the FTIR spectra. Therefore, ^1H NMR and FTIR results confirmed the occurrence of the click reaction between the pendant groups of the core PU-MAL and the sheath PU-SH. Moreover, it should be noted that since the hard segment of the polyurethanes did not crystallize, as deduced by DSC, those pendant groups were not confined in any rigid structure, that would facilitate the reaction.

Figure 3. A) ^1H NMR and B) FTIR spectra of the MALcoSH membranes before and after the click reaction.

The post-spinning click crosslinking of the membranes would allow the production of nanofibers from flexible thermoplastic polymers and their subsequent fast and damage-free reinforcement.

The effect of the crosslinking on the viscoelastic properties of the membrane was analysed by DMA. The measurements could only be completed on the clicked-MALcoSH membrane, as the MALcoSH membrane broke immediately after the test starting at -100 °C. Figure 4 shows the evolution of storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($E''/E' = \tan\delta$) with temperature of the clicked-MALcoSH membrane. As it could be observed, the curve shows that the membrane followed the predictable behaviour for a crosslinked segmented polyurethane. Indeed, at low temperatures, E' remained quasi-constant, later showing a significant drop together with the maximum in $\tan\delta$ value, due to the glass transition temperature of the soft segment, T_{gss} . After that, a continuous decrease of the storage modulus was observed, until the melting temperature of the soft segment, T_{mss} , was reached. Above T_{mss} , the storage modulus, even if it was quite low, remained constant, in accordance with the expected behaviour of a chemically crosslinked polymer, thus confirming the net points between the two complementary hard segments provided by the click reaction^{45,47}. Furthermore, it is worthy to note that the T_{gss} value was shifted from -52 °C, calculated by DSC analysis of the neat polyol, to -9 °C⁴⁵. This could be appointed to the crosslinking between the hard segments that strongly reduce the mobility of the whole polymeric chain, thus increasing the T_{gss} [31]. Finally, as shown in Figure 4, clicked-MALcoSH maintained its integrity after the test, while MALcoSH sample did not, as mentioned.

Figure 4. On the left DMA analysis of clicked-MALcoSH. On the right, clicked and not clicked MALcoSH samples.

The mechanical properties of MALcoSH and clicked-MALcoSH were analysed and compared by tensile tests, and the obtained results are shown in Figure 5. As it could be noticed, sharp differences were observed. In fact, in the case of clicked-MALcoSH, since the covalent bonding between the macromolecules was promoted along the nanofibers, remarkable stiffening of the membrane was measured due to the limited macromolecular mobility, as well as notable strength increase. The results thus corroborated the initial expectations, except for the elongation at break, which also increased after the click crosslinking. However, linear relationship between the crosslinking density and elongation at break is only true for densely crosslinked elastomers, which was not this case⁴⁹. The work of Choi et al., confirmed this last statements, showing that the crosslinking led to tougher membranes with definitively improved overall tensile behaviour¹⁵. The obtained membrane results in a tougher but less stretchable material with respect to other crosslinked nanofibrous membrane produced by coaxial electrospinning³⁸.

Figure 5 A) Stress-strain curve of clicked and not-clicked MALcoSH and B) mechanical properties of co-electrospun membranes before and after click reaction.

The morphological features of MALcoSH and clicked-MALcoSH membranes were analysed by SEM (Figure 6). The nanofibers showed good overall quality, better than those of neat PU-MAL, thanks to the good spinnability of the sheath PU-SH. As can be seen, deformation and merging of

the nanofibers occurred at contact points due to the low T_{gss} value (Figure S6)⁴⁸. This merging would lead to a certain chemical reaction between some nanofibers thus contributing to the robustness of clicked-MALcoSH. The calculated mean diameters were 336 ± 24 nm and 328 ± 32 nm for MALcoSH and clicked-MALcoSH, respectively, values in between those measured for PU-MAL and PU-SH individual membranes and similar to the ones produced by other studies⁴⁰ (Figure S 7). These results confirmed the suitability of the clicking reaction, minimally affecting size and surface properties of the nanofibers. Indeed, the morphology of the MALcoSH and clicked-MALcoSH was very similar and, as expected and desired when using miscible solvents for the preparation of the two electrospinning solutions, it was not possible to distinguish the core and sheath layers in the co-electrospun fibers.

Figure 6. SEM images of the surface and the cross-section (inset) of the electrospun membranes.

However, even if the sheath layer was PU-SH, which gave smooth nanofibers itself, certain surface roughness was detected in the coaxial nanofibers, similarly to that observed in PU-MAL ones. The surface roughness of the nanofibers would be also responsible of the hydrophobicity of the membranes. Indeed, PU-SH individual nanofibers, showed highly hydrophilic character (Figure S8), attributed to the free thiol pending groups on the surface. However, MALcoSH

presented hydrophobic surface, with the water drop absorption lasting over 2 minutes, probably due to the increased roughness given by the inner PU-MAL. Finally, clicked-MALcoSH showed an even higher hydrophobicity, due to both the increased roughness and to the low presence of free thiol groups available on the surface. The values for the water contact angle of MALcoSH and clicked-MALcoSH were found to be $115 \pm 3^\circ$ and $124 \pm 1^\circ$. The results of WCA analysis are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. WCA measurements of MALcoSH (left) and clicked-MALcoSH (right). The photos were taken every 30 seconds during 4 minutes.

The contribution of the crosslinking inside the nanofibers to the overall chemical stability of the membrane was also assessed. The capacity of the membrane to maintain its integrity in contact with organic solvents could be relevant for some applications, in particular for their use as filters or contaminant removers in organic solutions⁵⁰. That is why the gel content fraction, representing

the proportion of the insoluble part of a material, was measured. In the case of clicked-MALcoSH, it can be related to the crosslinking density. As can be seen from Figure 8, the gel content of the clicked-MALcoSH was always above the 60%, confirming the occurrence of the click crosslinking in the electrospun membrane.

Then, the chemical resistance to the same electrospinning mixture of solvents (DMF:CHCl₃ 2:1) of the MALcoSH and clicked-MALcoSH was tested by immersion (Figure 8). Images were taken before and after two hours immersion in the solvent mixture, at room temperature. As can be appreciated, MALcoSH was disintegrated in small pieces, while clicked-MALcoSH just swelled and maintained its original shape, demonstrating, once more, the effective crosslinking of the nanofibers.

Figure 8. Visual analysis of the chemical resistance to organic solvents of the not-crosslinked and crosslinked membranes (up) and gel fraction content calculated after the exposure to different solvents (down).

Once demonstrated the possibility to click crosslink the membrane electrospun with equimolar ratio of clickable moieties, the electrospun clicked membrane containing an excess of thiol (thiolated clicked-MALcoSH) was used for the adsorption of AgNPs from aqueous solution.

Indeed, the growing market of nanotechnologies implies the production and thus the possible release of a great variety of nano-entities in the environment. AgNPs are between the most commonly used nanoparticles and their toxicological effect can affect the environment, listing it between the new emerging contaminants^{51,52}. This is why new materials for the remediation of wastewater from AgNPs are needed. In this sense, several inorganic and noble metals nanoparticles have been reported to be reactive towards –SH group^{53–55} and thus the possibility to trap the silver nanoparticles on the thiolated clicked-MALcoSH was tested. The UV-vis spectra taken after 30 minutes (Figure 9) shows that the signal of AgNPs at 408 nm, completely disappeared and the solution shifted from the yellowish colour typical of the silver dispersion to a completely transparent liquid. The fast and quantitative adsorption of AgNPs, joined with the good mechanical and chemical resistance, are very promising for future application of the membrane in AgNPs remediation from wastewater.

Figure 9 UV-vis spectra of the AgNPs solution with thiolated clicked-MALcoSH

Finally, it was decided to perform a functionalization on thiolated clicked-MALcoSH nanofibrous membrane. As functionalizing agent was chosen 1H,1H,2H-Perfluoro-1-decene, a fluorinated alkene which is known to impart high liquid repellency thanks to its perfluoroalkyl chain⁵⁶. Effectively, as can be evinced from Figure S9 the initial WCA increased from $124 \pm 1^\circ$ of the clicked-MALcoSH to the $135 \pm 4^\circ$ of thiolated clicked-MALcoSH, that after 4 minutes still showed a WCA of 115° .

Conclusions

Two new complementarily clickable polyurethanes were synthesized and coaxially electrospun to a final membrane with homogeneous morphology and nanofibers' size. The prepolymer bulk polymerization method led to an accurate design of the polymeric backbone, by introducing clickable maleimide or thiol groups during the chain extension step in quantitative amount. The post-electrospinning crosslinking via thiol-maleimide Michael addition reaction demonstrated to be fast, tuneable, and reliable as reinforcement method. The obtained membranes showed improved mechanical overall performance, as well as resistance towards organic solvents and enhanced hydrophobicity. The strategy herein presented would not only led to robust nanofibers, but also membranes with specific surface functionalities could be designed by adjusting both flow rates and/or polymer ratios. Strong nanofibrous membranes with pendant thiol or maleimide groups as supports for immobilization of molecules of interest could be prepared.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. FTIR and labelled NMR spectra of DHPM, labelled NMR spectra of PU-MAL and PU-SH, further SEM characterization of the membranes and WCA of PU-SH membrane are presented in Supporting Information.

The following files are available free of charge.

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